

ACTION PLAN FOR THE REFORM OF RESEARCH EVALUATION AT THE UNIVERSITAT DE GIRONA (UdG)

Within the framework of the Coalition for the
Advancement of Research Evaluation (CoARA)

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1. Introduction and institutional context

The Universitat de Girona (UdG) is a public institution committed to the generation and transfer of knowledge, social responsibility and sustainability. Within this framework, the UdG accepts the challenge of transforming research evaluation systems, in line with the principles of the Coalition for the Advancement of Research Evaluation (CoARA) and with initiatives such as DORA, HRS4R and open science.

This commitment is based on a set of already consolidated institutional policies, such as:

- The Organisation of Research at the UdG (BOU 7100), which establishes the criteria for the promotion, recognition and support of research.
- The UdG's Environmental Plan, which promotes sustainable research aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).
- The Gender Equality Plan and the Anti-Harassment Protocol, which guarantee a safe, inclusive and equitable research environment.
- Ethical, child protection and data protection procedures that ensure integrity and accountability in research.
- The Open Access Mandate of the Universitat de Girona to promote the dissemination of scientific and academic production in open access.
- Adherence to the European Charter for Researchers and obtaining the HR Excellence in Research award, which recognises the UdG's efforts to offer an attractive and quality research environment.

This action plan is therefore part of a solid and coherent institutional trajectory, which seeks to consolidate a culture of evaluation that is fairer, plural and oriented towards the common good.

2. General objectives of the plan

The objectives of this action plan respond to the UdG's desire to place quality, responsibility and diversity at the centre of research evaluation. Specifically, it proposes to:

- Promote an evaluation based on the intrinsic value of scientific work, taking into account its relevance, rigour, social impact and contribution to open knowledge.
- Strengthen the culture of open science, recognising open access publication, FAIR data sharing, software development and participation in collaborative initiatives.
- Value the diversity of trajectories and contributions, including teaching, transfer, innovation, management, citizen participation and the gender dimension in research.
- Promote responsible research through the application of ethical protocols, data protection, the inclusion of the gender perspective and environmental sustainability.
- Guarantee equal opportunities and non-discrimination in evaluation processes, promoting transparency and the training of evaluation committees.

3. CoARA priority commitments adopted

The Universitat de Girona assumes the priority commitments of CoARA as a reference framework for research evaluation reform. These commitments are:

- a.** Recognise the diversity of research practices and results, including publications, data, software, technical reports, outreach, transfer and leadership activities.
- b.** Base the evaluation on qualitative criteria, such as scientific relevance, social impact, methodological coherence and adequacy to the values of responsible research.

- c. Use quantitative indicators responsibly, avoiding the exclusive use of metrics such as the Journal Impact Factor (IF) or the h-index, and promoting contextualised and transparent indicators.
- d. Promote transparency, inclusiveness and participation in evaluation processes, ensuring the representation of different profiles and the training of committee members.
- e. Promote the training and professional development of research staff and evaluators, with special attention to research ethics, open science, citizen science, collaborative research and the gender perspective.

4. Specific actions (2025–2027)

This plan is based on actions already initiated by the Universitat de Girona as part of its commitment to the reform of research evaluation. These actions include:

- Formal membership of CoARA, with the signing of the institutional agreement (2023).
- Active participation in the Spanish division of CoARA, including face-to-face meetings in Barcelona.
- Specific training for responsible evaluation, such as organised sessions on six-year plans and alternative indicators.
- Participation in external forums.
- Dissemination of resources and good practices through the website.
- Creation of the Open Science Commission, as an institutional body to promote policies aligned with CoARA.
- Implementation of the Programme for the retention and recruitment of excellent research talent, which incorporates quality criteria beyond traditional metrics.
- Ongoing actions:
 - Inclusion of responsible evaluation criteria in teaching and research staff recruitment.
 - Specific training from the Doctoral School.

These actions will be complemented by the following initiatives planned for the period 2025–2027:

Action	Description	Responsible person(s)	Calendar	Indicators
A1	Review the teaching and research staff evaluation criteria in internal calls (grants, promotion, six-year terms) to include responsible metrics and qualitative criteria.	Vice-Rectorate for Research Vice-Rectorate for Personnel Human Resources Service	2025	New criteria published and applied
A2	Create an institutional guide for the responsible evaluation of research, with examples and good practices.	BIBEC, Research Committee	2025	Guide published and disseminated
A3	Training for evaluation committees and teaching and research staff, and research support staff on CoARA, DORA and open science.	Doctoral School, Vice-Rector for Personnel Human Resources Service	2025–2026	Number of sessions and participants
A4	Explicit recognition of FAIR data, software and other results in internal calls.	Vice-Rectorate for Research	2026	Updated calls
A5	Active participation in national and international networks on evaluation reform.	Institutional representatives	2025–2027	Number of participations and collaborations

5. Monitoring and evaluation

The Open Science Commission will oversee the implementation of the plan. An annual review of progress will be conducted, and monitoring will be disseminated.

6. Conclusions

This action plan represents a firm step towards a culture of evaluation that is fairer, more inclusive and aligned with the values of open science and responsible research. The Universitat de Girona thus reaffirms its commitment to quality research, with social impact and oriented towards the common good.

The implementation of this plan not only responds to international demand, but also reinforces the UdG's own identity as a university rooted in its territory, committed to sustainability, equality and innovation. Through this process, the UdG aspires to become a benchmark in the transformative evaluation of research, at the service of society and shared knowledge.

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